

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE CRITERION: APPLICATION TO ORTHOTROPIC PLATES WITH CIRCULAR HOLES CALCULATED BY THE FINITE ELEMENT METHOD.

Baselga, S.; Peon, G. ;Piedrafita, G.; Casamayor, M.J.
University of Zaragoza-ICMA,SPAIN

C/ María de Luna, 3. 50015 Zaragoza.SPAIN. Tel: 976-51 74 01. FAX: 976- 51 29 32

ABSTRACT

On the basis of the results developed by Fu-Kuo Chang and Kuo-Yen Chang in relation with a progressive damage model for laminated composites containing stress concentrations, we are to combine them with the analysis of interlaminar stresses and the quadratic criterion of Tsai-Wu in order to obtain the modes of failure (as in plane as out of plane), and to predict the ultimate strength of orthotropic laminates containing centred circular holes.

Keywords: Stress concentration, finite elements, circular holes, progressive damage.

1. INTRODUCTION-SCIENCE STATE

Lekhnitskii developed an analytic model for orthotropic plates with centred circular holes. See figure -1-.

Figure 1. Orthotropic plate with circular hole

The stress profile at the edge of the hole is:

$$\sigma_{\vartheta} = P \left(\frac{E_{\vartheta}}{E_x} \right) \left\{ \left[-\cos^2 \varphi + (K + n) \sin^2 \varphi \right] K \cos^2 \vartheta + \right. \tag{1}$$

$$\left. + \left[(1 + n) \cos^2 \varphi - K \sin^2 \varphi \right] \sin^2 \vartheta - n(1 + K + n) \sin \varphi \cos \varphi \sin \vartheta \cos \vartheta \right\}$$

Where:

$$K = \sqrt{\frac{E_x}{E_y}}$$

$$n = \sqrt{2 \left(\sqrt{\frac{E_x}{E_y}} - \mu_{xy} \right) + \frac{E_x}{G_{xy}}} \quad (2)$$

When the load is applied in the direction of the principal axis "x", the stresses at points "B" and "B1" that are located in the diameter perpendicular to the load direction will have the known form:

$$\sigma_{\phi} = P (1 + n) \quad (3)$$

Gillespie developed an expression that quantified the new ultimate tensile strength due to the finite width of the specimen, that is:

$$\sigma_N^{\infty} = \sigma_N \left(\frac{K_t}{K_t^{\infty}} \right) \quad (4)$$

Where:

- σ_N^{∞} Ultimate tensile strength for an infinite plate with a circular hole
- σ_N Ultimate tensile strength for a finite plate with a circular hole
- K_t^{∞} Stress-concentration factor for an infinite plate
- K_t Stress-concentration factor for a finite plate

Where:

$$\frac{K_t}{K_t^{\infty}} = \frac{2 + (1 - D/W)^3}{3(1 - D/W)} \quad (5)$$

- D Diameter of the hole
- W Width of the plate

Inherent in this procedure is the assumption that the entire distribution of stress within the highly stressed region defined by $(R \leq y \leq W/2)$ scales with the parameter (K_t / K_t^{∞}) , then:

$$\frac{\sigma_x(0,y)}{\sigma_x^{\infty}(0,y)} = \left(\frac{K_t}{K_t^{\infty}} \right) = \text{Cte.} \quad (6)$$

Where $\sigma_x^{\infty}(0,y)$ is the tensile stress distribution in an infinite plate.

For laminates with " $(W / D) \leq 4$ ", $(\sigma_x / \sigma_x^{\infty})$ is a decreasing function of "y", the slope of the relation being dependent on orthotropy and (W / D) . Consequently, the finite width correction factor is valid only at the hole edge " $y = R$ " and significant error accumulates as the distance from the hole boundary increases.

To improve the representation of the stress profile adjacent to the hole where fracture initiates a non-dimensional function " $\delta(y)$ " is introduced, so that the finite width stress profile will be expressed in the following form:

$$\frac{\sigma_x(0,y)}{\sigma_x^\infty(0,y)} = \left(\frac{K_t}{K_t^\infty} \right) (1 + \delta(y)) \quad (7)$$

The function " $\delta(y)$ " quantifies the relative divergence of the true finite width stress profile defined in eqn. - 6 -, and it can be approximated as:

$$\delta(y) = -C(y - R) \left(\frac{K_t}{K_t^\infty} - 1 \right) \quad (8)$$

" $\delta(y)$ " has the following boundary conditions:

$$\delta(y=R) = 0 \quad -1 \leq \delta(y > R) \leq 0$$

"C" is the slope, and it is approximately equal to 0.070 mm^{-1} .

At this point, it is important to remember that on the grounds of the studies performed by Konish and Whitney, the stress distribution for an infinite orthotropic plate with a central hole of radius "R" is:

$$\sigma_x(0,y) = \frac{\sigma_x^\infty}{2} \left\{ 2 + \left(\frac{R}{y} \right)^2 + 3 \left(\frac{R}{y} \right)^4 - (K_t^\infty - 3) \left[5 \left(\frac{R}{y} \right)^6 - 7 \left(\frac{R}{y} \right)^8 \right] \right\} \quad (9)$$

for $y \geq R$

Figure 2. Axes of reference

By using the finite element method, the stress distribution in the whole specimen is calculated and so, both the results obtained through the previous theories and through the FEM, can be compared.

The mesh used was that showed in the next figure.

Figure 3. Mesh of the specimen

The specimen is to be symmetric as well as the load applied to it. The laminated studied is to be also symmetric and so, the number of finite elements will be a quarter of the elements that would be needed if all the specimen were meshed.

Every element in the mesh is volumetric with eight nodes, and its thickness corresponds to that of a ply.

Our goals are to calculate the stress profile in the specimen and through it, different failure criteria, the mode of failure and the ultimate strength will be determined.

2. METHOD OF APPROACH

The failure criteria selected to validate the theoretical approach by experimental tests is going to be:

a) Average stress criterion (A.S.C.)

The A.S.C. was proposed by Nuismer and Whitney. It assumes that failure occurs when the average stress value of " σ_x " over some fixed distance " a_0 ", ahead of the notch first reaches the unnotched tensile strength of the material; that is, for the circular hole, failure occurs when:

$$\frac{1}{a_0} \int_R^{R+a_0} \sigma_x(0,y) dy = \sigma_0 \quad (10)$$

This criterion is not suitable for a progressive damage model because it has got an unknown parameter " a_0 ", which depends on the material.

b) Progressive damage criteria

They are the most appropriate to use by the finite element method with progressive load and sequential calculation.

Fu-Kuo Chang and Kuo-Yen Chang presented three different in-plane failure modes to which we are going to add the interlaminar failure mode in order to determine its relative importance and to reflect all the modes of failure (in plane and out of plane).

For laminates with plies of very different stiffness it is interesting to add the stress concentrations due to free-edge phenomena.

For predicting matrix cracking failure, Chang proposed a criterion which has got the following form for laminates with linear behaviour:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_y}{Y_t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xy}}{S_c} \right)^2 = e_m^2 \quad (11)$$

Where:

- σ_y Transverse tensile stress in each layer
- σ_{xy} Shear stress in each layer
- Y_t Transverse tensile strength in each layer
- S_c In-plane shear strength in each layer

If $e_m \geq 1$ for any of the elements forming the plies in a laminate, then it is assumed that matrix cracking occurs for those elements and so, their properties are degraded according to the degradation model proposed for this kind of failure:

$$\begin{array}{lll} (E_x)_n = E_x & (G_{xy})_n = G_{xy} & (\mu_{xy})_n = \mu_{xy} \\ (E_y)_n = 0 & (G_{xz})_n = G_{xz} & (\mu_{xz})_n = \mu_{xz} \\ (E_z)_n = 0 & (G_{yz})_n = 0 & (\mu_{yz})_n = 0 \end{array}$$

Where $(-)_n$, indicate the new material properties in the damaged zone.

For predicting both fibre-matrix shearing and fibre breakage, the criterion proposed by Chang for laminates with linear behaviour, has the form:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_x}{X_t}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_{xy}}{S_c}\right)^2 = e_f^2 \quad (12)$$

Where:

- σ_x Longitudinal tensile stress in each layer
- σ_{xy} Shear stress in each layer
- X_t Longitudinal tensile strength in each layer
- S_c In-plane shear strength in each layer

If $e_f \geq 1$ for any of the elements forming the plies in a laminate, then it is assumed that matrix cracking occurs for those elements and so, their properties are degraded according to the degradation model proposed for this kind of failure:

$$\begin{array}{lll} (E_x)_n = d E_x & (G_{xy})_n = d G_{xy} & (\mu_{xy})_n = d \mu_{xy} \\ (E_y)_n = 0 & (G_{xz})_n = d G_{xz} & (\mu_{xz})_n = d \mu_{xz} \\ (E_z)_n = 0 & (G_{yz})_n = 0 & (\mu_{yz})_n = 0 \end{array}$$

Where "d" is a degradation parameter whose value is about 5% at the first step and subsequently it is decreased as the damaged area grows.

Finally, for predicting interlaminar failure, it is proposed the quadratic criterion of Tsai-Wu in the following form:

$$\left(\frac{\sigma_z}{Z}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{T}{S}\right)^2 = e_i \quad (13)$$

Where:

- σ_z Normal stress in each layer
- Z Normal tensile or compressive strength in each layer
- S Interlaminar shear strength in each layer

$$T^2 = \sigma_{xz}^2 + \sigma_{yz}^2$$

- σ_{xz} Interlaminar shear stress in the load direction
- σ_{yz} Interlaminar shear stress perpendicular to the load direction

When any of the interfaces in a laminate satisfies that $e_i \geq 1$, failure occurs in that interface.

Once failure occurs, the property degradation model proposed will vary depending on whether normal stresses are in tension or in compression:

a) $\sigma_z > 0$

$$\begin{array}{lll} (E_x)_n = E_x & (G_{xy})_n = G_{xy} & (\mu_{xy})_n = \mu_{xy} \\ (E_y)_n = E_y & (G_{xz})_n = 0 & (\mu_{zx})_n = 0 \\ (E_z)_n = 0 & (G_{yz})_n = 0 & (\mu_{zy})_n = 0 \end{array}$$

a) $\sigma_z < 0$

$$\begin{array}{lll} (E_x)_n = E_x & (G_{xy})_n = G_{xy} & (\mu_{xy})_n = \mu_{xy} \\ (E_y)_n = E_y & (G_{xz})_n = d_1 G_{xz} & (\mu_{zx})_n = d_1 \mu_{zx} \\ (E_z)_n = d_1 E_z & (G_{yz})_n = d_1 G_{yz} & (\mu_{zy})_n = d_1 \mu_{zy} \end{array}$$

Where "d₁" is a degradation parameter similar to the parameter "d" explained above.

3. PROPOSED STUDY

In order to corroborate the criteria previously described, tests considering different laminates and W/D ratios will be carried out. As the compositions as the geometries of the specimens have been chosen bearing in mind the parameters we want to study as well as the features of our tensile testing machine. They are described next

1) Laminates:

- 1a) (0/0/0/0)s resin epoxy reinforced with fibre glass
- 1b) (0/0/90/90)s resin epoxy reinforced with fibre glass
- 1c) (0/90/0/90)s resin epoxy reinforced with fibre glass

2) Geometry

The geometry of the specimens is showed in the next figure:

Figure 4. Geometry of the specimens

Where:

- 2a) $W/D = 12$ $D = 5$ mm $W = 60$ mm
- 2b) $W/D = 8$ $D = 5$ mm $W = 40$ mm
- 2c) $W/D = 4$ $D = 5$ mm $W = 20$ mm
- 2d) $W/D = 2$ $D = 5$ mm $W = 10$ mm

At the actual moment, most tests are not finished, that is why it is not possible to quantify the accuracy of the methods yet.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In spite of not having concluded the experimental test, it seems that it is more convenient the use of criteria based on progressive degradation than criteria based on stress distribution around the notch. The last ones are not able to determine the failure mode, and besides, the characteristic distances must be experimentally defined.

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